

Analytical and experimental investigations of trapezoidal sheet diaphragms: Comparative study on the shear stiffness of the analyzed configurations

Barnabás A. Lőrincz^{*,a}, Zsolt Nagy^a, Andrea R. Kelemen^a, Szabolcs B. Lőrincz Molnár^b

^aLTechnical University of Cluj-Napoca, Faculty of Civil Engineering, Romania
barnabas.lorincz@campus.utcluj.ro, zsolt.nagy@dst.utcluj.ro, andrea.dezo@mecon.utcluj.ro

^bIndependent researcher, Hungary
lorincz.szabolcs.botond@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Experimental investigations were conducted on different types of diaphragms in the Structures and Materials Research Laboratory of the Technical University of Cluj-Napoca. This paper focuses solely on the results of the trapezoidal sheet diaphragm tests and the associated analytical calculations.

The tested configurations can be identified as panel assemblies (diaphragm) with sheeting perpendicular to the length of the diaphragm and connecting to the supporting structure on two sides only. This type of diaphragm is not covered in the European Standard (1) since shear connectors are completely omitted. The tested configurations can be considered non-standard diaphragms, although they are commonly used in practice, highlighting the need to extend the design method for such configurations and the importance of updating the current design standard accordingly.

Furthermore, the established conventional methods for determining the experimental shear stiffness of the diaphragms proved to be inadequate for those fastened on two sides. Davies and Bryan (2) notes that flexibility of the diaphragm is defined as the reciprocal of the slope, considering the linear elastic segment of the load-deformation curve. However, the experimental investigations have revealed non-linear behaviour even in the initial loading stage of the diaphragm. Consequently, in this region, several tangent lines can be constructed due to variations in the slope and the initial tangent stiffness tends to overestimate this characteristic of the diaphragm.

The purpose of this paper is to compare the experimental and analytical shear flexibility of the tested configurations, to evaluate the existing and to propose additional procedures for determining the experimental shear stiffness of the trapezoidal sheet diaphragms. The proposed procedures were evaluated exclusively on the load-displacement curves of the tested specimens. Therefore, the applicability of the recommended methods is limited to the tested configurations and further investigations are required on a more comprehensive set of experimental or numerical data.

Keywords: stressed skin design, ECCS design expressions, experimental investigations, diaphragm stiffness.

1 INTRODUCTION

In 1995, the ECCS Committee TC7 published the document titled ‘European Recommendations for the application of metal sheeting as a diaphragm’ (1), establishing a standardized recommendation for the subject of the stressed skin design theory. Based on this publication (1), there are two main categories of diaphragms to consider when trapezoidal sheeting is oriented perpendicularly to the length of the diaphragm: the first is the diaphragm connected on all four sides to the supporting structure, which occurs when the sheeting is fixed to both the purlins and the parallel members; the second is the diaphragm attached on two sides to the supporting structure when the sheeting is connected only to the purlins. The second category can be divided into two sub-divisions: one where

diaphragms are connected to the main structure on two sides, with shear connectors (or their equivalent) only at the gable rafters and the other case is where shear connectors are completely omitted. The current European Standard (1) does not recommend the latter case, which involves no shear connectors at any rafters. However, the authors of the book (2) - which laid the theoretical foundation for the stressed skin design theory in 1982 - state that this arrangement may be used for lightly loaded diaphragms.

Since diaphragms fastened only on two sides to the supporting structure (which are mostly used in structural applications) represent non-standard arrangements, the authors of this paper intend to profoundly analyze and understand the behaviour of these configurations. Furthermore, the long-term goal of this research is to formally extend the current design procedure to these types of diaphragms. In Eastern Europe, where the authors conduct their investigations and structural design activities, the cladding systems of the steel portal frame structures are fixed on only two sides and considered as secondary elements in the majority of the cases.

Consequently, the authors have conducted numerous experimental investigations on isolated roof panel assemblies to quantify the structure-cladding interaction and to explore systematically the behaviour of these configurations in the context of two side fastened diaphragms. This research program is a necessity, as the structural design engineer can choose to consider or neglect these effects. Each decision leads to distinct technical considerations, currently not comprehensively addressed in design codes.

2 EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATIONS

Experimental investigations were carried out in the Structures and Materials Research Laboratory of the Technical University of Cluj-Napoca on various cladding systems, including configurations with sandwich panels and trapezoidal sheets connected to purlins. This paper focuses exclusively on the trapezoidal sheet diaphragm tests.

The test set-up used for the experimental investigations was presented in a previously published paper (3). The isolated panel selected for the tests consisted in two bays of 2.5 meters each, with a length of 3 meters. The marginal beams were fixed in all directions, while the middle beam was free to move in the direction of the beam axis. Throughout the experimental testing, a large displacement hydraulic jack was used to apply vertical movement to the middle beam, which was manually operated. The tested trapezoidal sheet diaphragm configurations are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Tested trapezoidal sheet configurations.

Test no.	Test code	Test no.	Test code
1	JA35-Z200-C-FET-S-DA	11	JA35-Z150-C-FET-S-DA
2	JA35-Z200-C-FAT-S-DA	12	JA35-Z150-C-FAT-S-DA
3	JA35-Z200-C-FET-S-DA-DS	13	JA16.5-Z150-C-FET-S-DA
4	JA35-Z200-C-FET-S-DA-WS	14	JA16.5-Z150-O-FET-S-DA
5	JA35-Z200-O-FET-S-DA	15	JP16.5-Z150-C-FET-S-DA
6	JA35-Z200-O-FAT-S-DA	16	JA16.5-Z150-O-FET-S-DA
7	JA16.5-Z200-C-FET-S-DA	17	JA35-Z200-C-FET-S-DB
8	JA35-JP16.5-Z200-C-FET-D-DA	18	JA35-Z200-C-FAT-S-DB
9	JA35-JP16.5-Z200-C-FAT-D-DA	19	JA16.5-Z200.1,5-C-FET-S-DA
10	JA35.0,75-Z200-C-FAT-S-DA	20	JA16.5-Z200.2,5-C-FET-S-DA

To illustrate the coding system of the configurations, consider the example of ‘JA35-Z200-C-FET-S-DA’. This code represents a specimen with trapezoidal sheets with a section height of 35 mm and a default thickness of 0.5 mm. The trapezoidal sheets of this configuration are fixed with the wider corrugations (JA) to the purlins in every trough (FET). The ‘Z’ shaped continuous (C) purlins have a height of 200 mm and a default thickness of 2.0 mm. This configuration is identified as a

single-skin (S) diaphragm, and the cleats are positioned in the strong direction (DA) on the mobile beam. Further details of the coding system are presented in paper (3).

The tested configurations allowed to observe the influence of several components on the stressed skin action. The trapezoidal sheets were manufactured by Joris Ide company and their steel grade was declared as S250GD+ZM. The configurations utilize Z150 and Z200 purlins, having theoretically S350GD+Z steel grade. The used seam fasteners were EJOT JT2-3-4.8x19 V14/2 type self-drilling screws and the sheet to purlin fasteners were JT2-6-5.5x25-V16 type self-drilling screws.

3 ANALYTICAL SHEAR STIFFNESS PREDICTIONS

This chapter focuses on presenting the standardized information available to the structural design engineers who wish to consider the stressed skin action during the design process of a steel portal frame structure. As a result, the authors have not made in this analytical study any improvements to the design expressions which would involve additional numerical or experimental investigations of the diaphragm's components. Therefore, they relied only on the information provided in the European Standard (1) and reference (2) for predicting the total flexibilities of the tested diaphragms.

The analytical approach presented in (1) is not applicable to the diaphragms tested in the current study, as these configurations were fastened to the main frame on only two sides and the shear connectors, or their equivalents, were completely omitted at the gable and central rafters. Consequently, to predict the flexibility of these non-standard diaphragms, an assumption from reference (2) was applied, which suggests that this type of arrangement may be used for lightly-loaded diaphragms. Furthermore, for such diaphragms, reference (2) provides a derived formula for calculating the shear flexibility due to connections to rafters (c_{23}), a component that is not covered by the European Standard (1) for these specific arrangements. During the analytical study of the tested configurations, the design expressions proved directly applicable for determining the total flexibility of only 9 specimens from the total 20 tested, for several reasons:

- Test no. 4: This specimen did not meet the necessary condition for satisfactory stressed skin action, as prescribed by European Standard (1), due to omission of seam fasteners, such as self-drilling screws between two adjacent sheets;
- Test no. 5, 6: These configurations used overlapped Z200/2 (2Z) purlins at the central rafters' cleat-purlin connections. For overlapped details, the European Standard (1) does not provide flexibility values (s_{pr}) for purlin to rafter connections, but suggests that the s_{pr} values may be obtained by test;
- Test no. 8, 9: these specimens were double-skin arrangements, which fall outside of the scope of the European Standard (1);
- Test no. 11, 12, 13: Z150/2 type purlins were used in the case of these configurations. The European Standard (1) does not offer purlin to rafter flexibility values (s_{pr}) for these type of purlin to rafter connections, but suggest that in these cases the s_{pr} values may be obtained by test;
- Test no. 14, 16: These configurations used overlapped (2Z) Z150/2 purlins at the central rafters' cleat-purlin connections. As it was previously outlined, the European Standard (1) does not provide flexibility values (s_{pr}) for these type of connections details;
- Test no. 15: This configuration used Z150/2 purlins and due to the specific geometry of the used trapezoidal sheet, the European Standard (1) does not provide all the necessary values in its tables to define the final 'K' term from the formula of the component (c_{11}).

In Table 2, the calculated values of the partial and total flexibilities of the nine "qualified" specimens are presented. These results were obtained based on the following assumptions:

- The 't' term from the design formulas represents the core thickness of the trapezoidal sheets, excluding zinc and other metallic coating layers. For the analytical study, a standard zinc coating of 0.04 mm was considered, as referenced in Eurocode (4);
- The modulus of elasticity (E) of the material from which the trapezoidal sheet was manufactured was assumed to be the theoretical value of 210 kN/mm²;

- The slip values for sheet to purlin and seam fasteners (s_p and s_s), as provided in Table 5.1 of the European Standard (1), are derived from test results and should be considered approximate. These values are applicable for trapezoidal sheet thicknesses ranging from 0.5 mm to 1.2 mm. Within this specific thickness range, the European Standard (1) specifies that the slip values are independent of the material's yield strength and the components' thicknesses;

- In the case of the tested configurations, the purlin to rafter connection was applied as a common cleat detail used in current structural design practice. However, this specific detail is not included in Table 5.3 from European Standard (1), which contains the design strengths (F_{pr}) and flexibilities (s_{pr}) for purlin to rafter connections. For this reason, the flexibility value for the purlin to rafter connection (s_{pr} value) used in the analytical study is an approximation. In this analysis, connection type 10 from Table 5.3 was selected to determine the partial flexibility of the connection to rafters (c_{23}).

Based on these assumptions, it can be concluded that the analytical flexibility values of the tested diaphragms should be used exclusively for making predictions and identifying behavioural trends in stressed skin action. This approach allows to evaluate the influence of different parameters on the stressed skin action and to identify the components that contribute significantly to the total flexibility of the analyzed configurations. Moreover, the obtained partial flexibility values are presented as percentages of the total flexibility as well (Table 2).

Table 2. Total flexibility predictions for tested configurations, based on the analytical procedure presented in (1, 2)

Test no.	$c_{1.1}$ [mm/kN]	$c_{1.1}$ [%]	$c_{1.2}$ [mm/kN]	$c_{1.2}$ [%]	$c_{2.1}$ [mm/kN]	$c_{2.1}$ [%]	$c_{2.2}$ [mm/kN]	$c_{2.2}$ [%]	$c_{2.3}$ [mm/kN]	$c_{2.3}$ [%]	c_3 [mm/kN]	c_3 [%]	c [mm/kN]
1	0.376	39.82	0.030	3.17	0.040	4.26	0.049	5.20	0.440	46.54	0.009	1.01	0.945
2	2.331	77.99	0.030	1	0.081	2.69	0.051	1.71	0.487	16.28	0.009	0.32	2.990
3	0.376	40.75	0.030	3.25	0.040	4.36	0.027	2.98	0.440	47.63	0.009	1.03	0.924
7	0.081	14.05	0.028	4.81	0.027	4.63	0.043	7.40	0.390	67.45	0.009	1.65	0.578
10	0.787	54.89	0.019	1.36	0.081	5.61	0.051	3.57	0.48	33.91	0.009	0.66	1.435
17	0.376	39.82	0.030	3.17	0.040	4.26	0.049	5.20	0.440	46.54	0.009	1.01	0.945
18	2.331	77.99	0.030	1	0.081	2.69	0.051	1.71	0.487	16.28	0.009	0.32	2.990
19	0.081	13.97	0.028	4.79	0.027	4.60	0.043	7.36	0.390	67.07	0.013	2.22	0.581
20	0.081	14.10	0.028	4.83	0.027	4.64	0.043	7.42	0.390	67.69	0.007	1.31	0.576

4 EXPERIMENTAL SHEAR STIFFNESS DETERMINATION

This section presents the existing procedures for evaluating the experimental shear stiffness of diaphragms. Additionally, the authors developed new methodologies and refined existing procedures which offer promising directions to estimate this parameter. However, the newly developed approaches have limitations, as they were tested solely on the specific diaphragm configurations used in the presented experiments and further refinement is possible.

In the fundamental book (2) on the subject of stressed skin design, the shear flexibility of a diaphragm is defined as the reciprocal of the slope of the linear elastic portion of the experimental load-displacement curve. However, the experimental investigations of this study have revealed that even in the initial loading stage the diaphragm exhibit non-linear behaviour. Consequently, in this region, several tangent lines can be constructed due to variations in the slope. Assuming that the initial slope of the elastic range represents the stiffness of the diaphragms, tends to overestimate the value of this parameter (Fig. 1). Due to this fact, it is necessary to evaluate the experimental shear stiffness of the diaphragms using alternative methods also. These approaches are presented in the following sections.

Fig. 1 a) Test no. 2 - Initial tangent stiffness

Fig. 1 b) Test no. 10 - Initial tangent stiffness

4.1 Method presented in ECCS No. 88 (1)

The design value of the shear flexibility of a diaphragm can be determined from the experimental load-displacement curve using the following formula from reference (1):

$$c = \frac{\Delta}{0.6V_d} \quad (1)$$

where c is the design value of the shear flexibility,
 Δ is the mean deflection at a load of $0.6V_d$,
 V_d is the design capacity of the tested diaphragm.

This methodology is, to the authors' knowledge, the only standardized method within Europe for determining the design value of the shear flexibility of the diaphragms using experimental data. However, the scope of the current study is to define the experimental shear flexibility of the tested configurations. Therefore, in formula (1), the design capacity of the specimens is substituted with the experimentally obtained shear strength of the tested diaphragms which does not coincide with the ultimate test load of the configurations. The experimental shear strength is defined as the peak load, observed immediately before the first significant reduction in force during the tests (Fig 2a). Afterwards, the experimental shear stiffness/flexibility of the diaphragm is obtained by using the presented method (Fig. 2b).

Fig. 2 a) Test no. 1 – Experimental shear strength of the specimen

Fig. 2 b) Test no. 1 – Determining the diaphragm's experimental flexibility – adapted method from (1)

4.2 Method described in CFSRC R-2017-02 (5)

The approach for determining the experimental shear stiffness (G'), described in (5), aligns closely with the previously presented European method, but slightly differs in its implementation.

According to this procedure, the experimental shear stiffness is defined as the secant stiffness at a load level corresponding to 40% of the diaphragm's maximum strength (S_{max}). This value is obtained by drawing a secant line from the origin of the experimental force-displacement curve to the point where the load is equal to 40% S_{max} (Fig 3a). In this study, the maximum strength of the diaphragms was replaced by the experimental shear strength of the diaphragms (Fig. 3b), determined as described in section 4.1.

Fig. 3 a) Determination of the experimental shear stiffness – method described in (5)

Fig. 3 b) Test no. 2 – Determining the diaphragm's experimental flexibility – adapted method from (5)

4.3 Adapted ECCS No. 45 (6) method

This approach integrates the principles described in reference (6), which is a document focused on testing procedures for assessing the behaviour of structural steel elements under cyclic loads. Additionally, it includes several definitions for the yield point of structural elements under monotonic tests (first phase). The general definition, which identifies this characteristic point as the intersection of two specific tangent lines, was adapted.

The procedure begins by determining the initial slope of the elastic range (the stiffness of the structural element), where the first tangent line is fitted to the load-displacement curve from its origin. The following step involves drawing a secondary tangent line with a slope that is one-tenth of the initial tangent line's slope. The intersection of these tangent lines marks the yield point of the tested structural element. In the proposed method, the intersection point is projected horizontally onto the load-displacement curve of the analyzed diaphragms to establish the elastic range limit (Fig. 4a).

Fig. 4 a) Test no. 17 – Determining the elastic range limit with the adapted method – adapted method from (6)

Fig. 4 b) Test no. 17 – Determining the diaphragm's experimental flexibility – adapted method from (6)

Subsequently, a trendline is fitted up to this limit to estimate the diaphragm's experimental shear stiffness (Fig. 4b), defined as the reciprocal of the diaphragm's flexibility.

4.4 Developed method 1

In this method, a cubic smoothing spline representation was developed to accurately model the load-displacement curve, which exhibits a complex pattern. The spline's smoothing factor (s) was determined to be the product of the standard deviation of the data and the number of registered data points, as recommended in (7). The experimental shear strength of the diaphragm was determined by finding the first local maximum of the fitted spline (Fig. 5a).

Fig. 5 a) Test no. 1 – Polynomial fitting to load-displacement curve up to the experimental shear strength

Fig. 5 b) Test no. 1 – Determining the elastic range limit with Z-score filtering

Furthermore, a third-degree polynomial model was fitted to the load-displacement curve up to the experimental shear strength of the diaphragm (Fig. 5b), and its first derivative function was analytically computed and evaluated. The derivative values underwent a z-score filtering process to determine the elastic range limit of the load-displacement curve of the tested diaphragms. Consequently, those displacement values (x) were filtered out, where the difference between the derivative (d_x) and the average derivative value (μ) was lower than -0.25 times the standard deviation (σ) of the derivatives (eq. 2).

As a next step, a trendline was fitted to the polynomial up to the elastic range limit, its slope representing the experimental shear stiffness of the diaphragm (Fig. 6).

$$Z_x = \frac{d_x - \mu}{\sigma} \leq -0.25 \quad (2)$$

where Z_x is the standard score,
 d_x derivative of the data point,
 μ the mean of the sample (polynomial),
 σ standard deviation of the sample (polynomial).

Fig. 6 a) Test no. 1 – Experimental shear stiffness

Fig. 6 b) Test no. 3 – Experimental shear stiffness

4.5 Developed method 2

This method relies on calculating the Pearson correlation coefficient (r) between 1mm displacement and an upper displacement limit to evaluate linearity in the analyzed segment. The lower 1mm threshold is employed to disregard the initial high stiffness of the tested configurations. The criterion for linearity is set at $r > 0.99$. The process involves systematically shifting the upper limit through the registered displacement values in 1mm increments. For each interval between 1mm and the current upper limit the Pearson correlation coefficient is registered. Subsequently, the algorithm identifies the longest linear portion by comparing these coefficients to the given linearity criterion and extracting the corresponding upper limit, which is the equivalent of the elastic range limit. Afterwards, a trendline is fitted on the ‘linear-elastic’ portion of the load-displacement curve. The slope of this trendline represents the stiffness of the specimen, which is the reciprocal of the experimental shear flexibility of the diaphragm (Fig. 7).

Fig. 7 a) Test no. 3 – Determining the diaphragm’s experimental flexibility with developed method 2

Fig. 7 b) Test no. 7 – Determining the diaphragm’s experimental flexibility with developed method 2

5 DISCUSSION OF RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

In the analytical study the authors relied only on the information provided in the European Standard (1) and reference (2) for predicting the total flexibilities of the tested diaphragms. As a result, the existing formal methodology available for structural design engineers was applicable to only 9 of the 20 tested configurations. These limitations highlight also the need to extend and update the current analytical procedures. Such an update or revision should also involve the extension of the databases that include values for the flexibilities and strengths of commonly used details in typical sheet to purlin and purlin to rafter connections.

The evaluation of the analytical procedure’s results clearly demonstrates the major contributions of $c_{1,1}$ (sheet distortion) and $c_{2,3}$ (purlin to rafter connection) in total flexibility. These results indicate a specific trend: $c_{2,3}$ becomes the dominant flexibility component when the trapezoidal sheets are attached to the purlins in every trough. Moreover, $c_{1,1}$ is identified as the predominant factor when the sheets are connected to the perpendicular members in alternate troughs. These trends suggest that in configurations with sheets fixed in every trough, investigating the behaviour of sheet to purlin and purlin to rafter connections is crucial. Conversely, in configurations with sheets fixed in alternate troughs, the geometry of trapezoidal sheets significantly influences the total flexibility.

The analytical study indicates that the most flexible configurations are those in which the trapezoidal sheets were fixed to the purlins in alternate troughs (Test no. 2, 10, 18). This tendency is generally reflected during the experimental study, reinforcing the ability of the analytical procedures to predict and identify behavioural trends in stressed skin action. However, the analytical predictions for Test no. 2 and Test no. 18 does not align with the experimental results. Configuration no. 18. exhibited greater flexibility than configuration no. 2 while the analytical method predicted an

identical value for both. The only distinction between these two specimens was the loading direction (rafters' cleats rotated with 180 degree) of the diaphragms. The significance of this parameter was previously addressed in reference (8) and now has been confirmed through experimental data, indicating the necessity of integrating and considering the direction of the loading when determining values for purlin to rafter flexibility.

Figure 8 presents a comparative analysis of these flexibility values, both analytical and experimental, for the 'qualified' tested configurations (specimens to which the analytical design expressions were applicable). A notable discrepancy exists between the experimental values and the corresponding analytical values, resulting in lower flexibilities in certain cases and significantly higher in others. It can be observed that the initial slope method along with the approach described in CFSRC R-1017-02 (5) proved to be the most conservative in terms of flexibility, providing the lowest flexibility values from the 6 methods. These methods are effective only in estimating the flexibility of the diaphragms in lightly-loaded stages.

Fig. 8. Comparative study of the nine 'qualified' specimens' shear flexibility

The experimental research program demonstrates that the tested specimens exhibited non-linear behaviour even in the initial loading stage. Consequently, it becomes challenging to establish a specific point for the elastic range limit on the load-displacement curves or to accurately identify their linear portion. Therefore, the determination of this parameter might be more effectively achieved using statistical approaches combined with empirical values, which can estimate the region where the elastic range limit may lie.

The existing and adapted procedures define the flexibility values based on a single specific characteristic of the load-displacement curve and do not consider the diaphragms' average behaviour. Due to this fact, these methods are less reliable in case of the two side fastened diaphragms, where non-linear behaviour is intercepted before the ultimate limit state of the specimens. The initial slope method and the adapted method described in section 4.3. derives flexibility values using the first registered data. Furthermore, methods presented in CFSRC R-1017-02 (5) and in reference (1) define the experimental shear flexibility in relation to the shear strength of the diaphragms.

The authors have developed two distinct methods to address these limitations. These approaches are formulated to consider the diaphragms' average behaviour in the experimental flexibility determination process. The experimental flexibility values obtained through these methods show consistency across all test configurations, revealing similar trends and offering promising directions to estimate this parameter. However, the newly developed approaches have limitations, as they were evaluated solely on the tested trapezoidal sheet diaphragm configurations and further refinement might be possible.

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